

KONIECZNOŚĆ UCZENIA SIĘ TERMINOLOGII ANGIELSKIEJ Z ZAKRESU TURYSTYKI I HOTELARSTWA W CELU ROZWOJU NAWYKÓW KOMUNIKACYJNYCH

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Adnotacja. Umiejętności komunikacyjne są kluczowym elementem w branży hotelarskiej i turystycznej. Jak większość innych sektorów turystyka oraz hotelarstwo mają swoją terminologią specjalistyczną, którą należy się nauczyć i posługiwać. W tej branży mamy do czynienia przez dłuższy czas z ludźmi, dlatego niezbędnym jest umiejętność udzielani instrukcji oraz informacji wyjaśniających. Zadaniem niniejszego artykułu jest prezentacja bieżących potrzeb zarządzania turystyką i hotelarstwem na Ukrainie z punktu widzenia wydajności języków obcych jako pierwszy krok w kierunku nadania przyszłym fachowcom przewagi konkurencyjnej dzięki opracowaniu pomyslnych programów naukowych oraz metodyki kształcenia wyższego w celu poznania leksyki specjalistycznej dla doskonalenia umiejętności językowych w branży turystycznej i hotelarskiej. Dlatego też w kolejnym artykule zostanie przeprowadzony przegląd literatury międzynarodowej dotyczącej danego zagadnienia. Zostanie również zaprezentowany proces badawczy na którym opierają się kolejne badania i będą prezentowane jego najważniejsze wyniki, a także będą zalecane przyszłe badania.

Słowa kluczowe: nawyki z zakresu języka obcego, turystyka i hotelarstwo, nauka terminologii, umiejętność posługiwania się językiem, kompetencja międzykulturowa, program podwyższenia kwalifikacji, nośniki nie nośniki językowe, efektywna komunikacja.

THE NECESSITY OF TEACHING ENGLISH TERMINOLOGY OF TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY TO DEVELOP SPEAKING SKILLS

Abstract In the tourism and hospitality industry, communication is a key factor. Like most other sectors, tourism and hospitality has its own set of jargon that it's important to learn and understand. In this industry you'll be dealing with people a lot of the time, and you'll need to ensure you can make recommendations, give instructions and explain situations clearly. The current paper aims at highlighting the current needs of hospitality management in Ukraine in terms of efficiency in foreign languages, as the first step towards offering future hospitality employees a competitive advantage through the development of successful higher education curricula and methodologies to master the specific vocabulary for perfect communication in the career of tourism and hospitality. Therefore, in following the international literature will be reviewed, the research process the current paper is based on will be presented and its most significant findings as well as recommended concrete actions and future research will be highlighted.

Keywords: foreign language skills, tourism and hospitality industry, vocabulary teaching, language proficiency, intercultural competence, in-service training programme, native and non-native speakers, effective communication

НЕОБХІДНІСТЬ НАВЧАННЯ АНГЛІЙСЬКОЇ ТЕРМІНОЛОГІЇ З ТУРИЗМУ ТА ГОТЕЛЬНОГО БІЗНЕСУ ДЛЯ РОЗВИТКУ НАВИЧОК ГОВОРІННЯ

Анотація. У галузі туризму та готельного бізнесу спілкування є ключовим чинником. Як і більшість інших секторів, туризм та готельний бізнес мають свій набір жаргону, який важливо вивчити та розуміти. У цій галузі ви будете мати справу з людьми багато часу, і вам потрібно буди впевненим що ви можете робити рекомендації, дати інструкції та чітко пояснити ситуації. Ця стаття має за мету висвітлити поточні потреби управління туризмом та готельним бізнесом в Україні з точки зору ефективності іноземних мов як перший крок на шляху до надання майбутнім фахівцям конкурентної переваги завдяки розробці успішних навчальних програм та методики вищої освіти для вивчення конкретної лексики для досконалого спілкування в кар'єрі туризму та готельного бізнесу. Тому, в наступній статі буде розглянута міжнародна література з даного питання, буде представлений процес дослідження на якому базується наступне дослідження, і будуть висвітлені його найважливіші результати, а також рекомендовані конкретні заходи та майбутні дослідження.

Ключові слова: навички іноземної мови, індустрія туризму та готельного бізнесу, навчання лексики, вміння володіти мовою, міжкультурна компетентність, програма підвищення кваліфікації, носії та не носії мови, ефективне спілкування.

Introduction. Taking into consideration the vast importance of tourism and hospitality industry for the economic prosperity of Ukraine and its people, hospitality management representatives have to strive to assure customer satisfaction, as the best way to assure profits and blooming business, while at the same time young people interested in maximizing their chances of being employed in this prosperous yet highly competitive field have to be adequately trained to succeed in the global hospitality market place. The role of foreign languages in the delivery of quality service is significant in that they are an important tool to make a guest feel at home, hence draw more brand loyalty and larger cash flows.

Language acts an essential part of success in hospitality, and has impacted the hospitality industry continuously. Not only has it influenced the method of marketing strategies or the methods of human resource management, it has also influenced the educational system as well. Many have come to realize that foreign language skills can be utilized in the industry to assist the foreign traveler, communicate with non-English speaking-employees and to work in non-English speaking countries.

Foreign language in the hospitality industry is needed to assist foreign travelers. The hospitality industry is a service industry that sets to provide service to achieve the customers' satisfactions. Customers are seeking for exceptional and customized service that fits them well. A made-to-measure service usually comes from organizing matters that the customers are used to, such as a guests' favorite drink, preferred room type, and the spoken language is a part of it as well. Of many tourists that travels, it is likely that they may not excel in the language of the foreign country that they are traveling to. If an accommodation that the customer is staying is not able to provide quality service due to the fact that miscommunication occurs frequently, the customer is likely to develop a negative opinion towards this certain hotel or restaurant. Therefore, the hospitality industries usually adapt ourselves to the customer's preference by providing multi-lingual service in order to support the customers' needs.

In the tourism and hospitality industry, communication is a key factor. You'll spend a lot of time meeting people's needs, providing services, and solving problems. Even on an international scale, generally it is English that you'll need to be proficient in, although you will come into contact with people from all around the world.

Like most other sectors, tourism and hospitality has its own set of jargon that it's important to learn and understand. In this industry you'll be dealing with people a lot of the time, and you'll need to ensure you can make recommendations, give instructions and explain situations clearly.

The current paper aims at highlighting the current needs of hospitality management in Ukraine in terms of efficiency in foreign languages, as the first step towards offering future hospitality employees a competitive advantage through the development of successful higher education curricula and methodologies to master the specific vocabulary for perfect communication in the career of tourism and hospitality. Therefore, in following the international literature will be reviewed, the research process the current paper is based on will be presented and its most significant findings as well as recommended concrete actions and future research will be highlighted.

There have been international studies examining the consumers' language preferences. Holmqvist et al. (2014) have found that tourists who receive service in a language other than their first one are less likely to leave tips or to recommend the service to others. But even more important consumers tend to fear that they will not be correctly understood if using a second language, either because they do not trust their language proficiency level or because they judge some topics of communication as very important. According to Grewal et al. (cited in Holmqvist et al., 2014) feeling in control over the service the tourists are receiving affects their whole perception of the level of service received. Therefore, being allowed to express needs and wishes in the mother tongue relieves unnecessary tension. Language is also found to have an emotional correlation with the guests' attitudes (*Holmqvist et al., 2014*) regarding a sense of community with people who share the same language, and an identification with the company that uses it making them feel at home away from home (Poon & Low, 2005).

Foreign language skills have indeed been identified as important managerial skills by several researchers. Managers should be equipped with both communicative and intercultural competence to be able to adapt and excel in the competitive work environment and foreign languages are the way to avoid stereotypes and gain insight into foreign people's mentality (*Zorina et al., 2014*). As cited in Russel et al. (2004) fluency in foreign languages is also a key element in developing business links with overseas business partners or foreign colleagues. The Rwanda Skills Survey (2012) reports linguistic competence to be the most wanted skill in globally known tourist destinations, such as Mauritius and United Emirates of Arabia.

Vizental argues that, as regards vocabulary, for quite a long time, there used to be a prejudice according to which vocabulary teaching was equivalent to providing students with long lists of isolated words, generally organized in semantic fields, but not contextualized, which had to be learned by heart (*Vizental, 2008*) (e.g. "jobs in tourism": travel and information consultant, cellar man, restaurant greeter, tour guide, sommelier, concierge, outdoor recreation guide, resort manager, night audit clerk etc.). E. Frenzo has demonstrated this was a totally restrictive view, since "lexical words" represent just one category within vocabulary, the most numerous undoubtedly, but there are also "function words" (such as determiners, pronouns, prepositions,

conjunctions, modal verbs, wh-words), which make the connection between lexical words and which are also part of vocabulary (*Frendo, 2005*).

In addition, teaching vocabulary should always involve teaching “multi-word units”/ “lexical phrases”/ “chunks of language”/ “collocations”/ “word partnerships”. E.g.: tourist accommodation sector, travel agent, package tour, growth rate, domestic trip, outbound trip, go on + expedition/ business trip/ guided tour/ voyage, take a risk. Elements related to register and colligation should also be addressed when teaching vocabulary. The latter refers to the grammatical relations between words, being considered a grouping of words which occur in particular syntactic patterns. E.g.: the pattern “the+adj.- superlative+noun+to+verb” (e.g. the best time to visit, the most amazing country to see, the most popular way to get), “prep.+the+noun: city” (e.g. around/ in/ from/ of the city) (*Blue, 2003*). Word formation issues represent another aspect connected to teaching vocabulary, and not only the common one, but also initialisms – abbreviations and acronyms (e.g. ETA: estimated time of arrival, RFP: request for proposal, LOS: length of stay, WTO: World Tourism Organization, TOS: Tour operators, R&B: room and board) and blendings – the merging of two lexemes in a single term (e.g. travelogue: travel + catalogue, traveller: travel + escalator, stagflation: stagnation + inflation, campsite: camping + site, ecotourism: ecological + tourism etc.) (*Dudley-Evans, 1998*).

Among the topics which tend to be present in most of the materials supporting the teaching and learning of grammar, vocabulary and language skills for tourism, we can mention: Travelling and Holidays, Countries and Nationalities, Employment in Tourism, Accommodation, Hotel Structure and Staff, Food and Restaurants, Sightseeing, Tour Guides, Tour Operators, Using the Telephone, Reservations, Complaints and Adjustments, Types of Tourism, Money and Payment etc. As types of activities to enhance the linguistic competence, the most frequently used ones mentioned in the specialized literature are: word formation, verbs in brackets, multiple matching, translations, find words/ phrases for explanations given, open cloze, error correction, information transfer, multiple choice.

The last skill which the discourse competence has to cover is speaking, which seems to represent a priority both for learners and for future specialists, being given that they are very often involved in spoken exchanges. This importance attached to speaking, however, is accompanied by a significant degree of difficulty, a perception which may be due to the insufficient lack of language proficiency, to the fear of making mistakes and thus losing face. The most important discourse competences in point of speaking are considered the following: the ability to explain and persuade, delivering good extemporaneous presentations, efficiently speaking on the phone, using appropriate language during meetings and discussions. Some types of activities for developing speaking skills would be: oral drills, information gap activities, comparing and contrasting pictures, individual or group presentations, presentations based on notes, group/ class discussions, debates, case studies, role plays, interpreting ideas from texts/ audio messages.

People who work in the travel industry around the world generally use English as a common language to communicate with international tourists. This not only includes tour guides, but also people working in hotels, restaurants, transportation services and more. You could work in a bakery in a busy tourist district, as a taxi driver, a hotel receptionist or even a bike tour guide.

Because there are so many jobs in tourism, there are many different types of tourism English. If you're looking at a job in this dynamic, international industry, you'll discover that your daily responsibilities require a special set of vocabulary.

This special vocabulary allows you to:

- Answer tourists' questions
- Give recommendations
- Provide directions
- Engage in small talk and make friendly conversation
- Describe places

Learning academic English is a common part of schooling in most countries.

However, people who work in the tourism industry often choose to take additional courses in "tourism English." These courses help them get prepared for scenarios like the ones described above. But why?

In the English dialogue examples that you hear in class or online, there are usually two native English speakers talking.

In real life, it's possible that your conversations will be between two non-native speakers of English — you and your guest or customer.

Therefore, working in the tourism industry requires that you're able to communicate effectively with native and non-native speakers of English.

Knowing the customs of English-speaking countries is helpful, but not all tourists you meet come from Great Britain, Australia, Canada and the United States. Many tourists are non-native speakers of English just like you!

In particular, intercultural competence is acquired during in-service training (both in Ukraine and abroad) during which the trainees meet representatives of different cultures and nationalities and face different situations and have to solve the arisen problems. The number of FIT students undergoing in-service training abroad has increased from 81 to 151 during the last 4 years (an increase of 1.86 times) that clearly illustrates the point. During the practice work students acquire the essential skills and real experience of working in a multicultural environment in other countries thereby compensating for similar relatively limited opportunities in Ukraine.

The 4-year professional bachelor study programme "Tourism and Hospitality Management" foresees 3 annual 4 week long compulsory in-service training in tourism and hospitality enterprises in Ukraine or abroad that is evaluated as 14 credit points (21 ECTS). However, taking into account the seasonality factor in tourism and hospitality, students work at least 3 months during in-service training in foreign enterprises thereby gaining additional experience as well as income.

The in-service training programme has been designed to integrate into practice the theoretical knowledge gained by the students during the respective study year, gaining additional in depth knowledge with every consecutive year. The aims of the in-service training for each study year are different and orientated at achieving a certain set of skills and abilities required to manage an enterprise and are in accordance to the strategic aims and tasks. For e.g. the aim for the first year in-service training is "acquire and develop practical skills in hospitality enterprises, implement them in real life situations, acquire and use communicative and sales skills while working with clients, gain an insight of the products and services offered by the enterprise, pricing, basic calculations and the operations on the whole, get acquainted with the use of various technologies as well as the sense of responsibility required for employees working in

the tourism and hospitality sector”. On the other hand, the aim of the 3rd year in-service training is “to provide students the opportunity to gain a set of economic competences and practical skills necessary for managers of tourism and hospitality enterprises to carry out economic, administrative and social activities, acquire the latest management methods, multifaceted marketing techniques, financial stability principles and legal aspects of various operations”.

The tasks are set according to the aims and the students’ field of specialization: Hotel Administration, Restaurant Administrator, Tour Consultant and Organizer, Tour Guide, and Leisure and Recreation Organizer.

During the in-service training the student acquaints himself with the enterprise operations in accordance to the programme. The majority of students work as waiters, barmen, animators (in foreign enterprises) or in hotel operations and front desk departments, as travel consultants in travel agencies and tourist information centers, etc. The students’ practice reports indicate that they highly evaluate training on a rotation basis, which is quite often difficult for enterprises to arrange. Upon conclusion of in-service training students not only evaluate their own achievements and skills gained but also the operations of the respective enterprises in accordance to the in-service training programme.

Before compilation of bachelor theses, students undergo a 12 week long pre-diploma training (12 credits or 18 ECTS), mainly aimed at gathering materials in the respective field for successful compilation of bachelor theses. To sum up, students’ in-service training is an important component of the study process and alongside with other study courses it promotes students’ intercultural competence.

In the international world of tourism, you’ll discover a diverse mix of native and non-native speakers who come from a variety of linguistic backgrounds. Therefore, it’s critical that people working in the tourism industry develop strategies for understanding new English accents and being prepared for tricky situations that might arise.

To help our students, we’ve come up with some tips for effective communication with international English speakers. You’ll practice how to check for clarification, politely communicate that you didn’t understand something and handle common scenarios where miscommunication can occur.

If you work in the tourism industry, you probably have experience with miscommunication.

As a guide, host or receptionist, it’s your job to make sure that you’re double-checking for understanding. These phrases are simple and quick ways to make sure you and your guest are on the same page.

- I heard you ask (about flights). Is that correct?
- So, you said (you wanted to visit the ruins), right?
- Okay, I understand that (your flight leaves at 3 PM). Is that correct?

Even though you’re both speaking English, your guest may use vocabulary that you’re unfamiliar with. Likewise, they might have an accent that’s difficult for you to understand. Here are some polite ways to ask them to repeat or clarify what they said.

- I’m sorry, I didn’t quite understand that. Can you say that again?
- Pardon my English, but I didn’t quite understand that. Can you say that again?
- I’m sorry, but I didn’t catch that. Can you describe what you mean?

Some cultures encourage people to be outspoken, while those from other parts of the world prefer people to act in a more reserved manner. Make all of your guests feel welcome by encouraging them to ask questions.

- Does anyone have any questions?
- Yes, sir/ma'am? Do you have a question?
- Please feel free to raise your hand any time if you have a question.
- So, any questions?

Depending on your job, you'll probably be required to give directions to tourists, provide them with recommendations for a good restaurant or attraction and in general make friendly conversation that makes them feel welcome.

In these scenarios, you'll play the part of the "guide", but it could really be anyone a tourist might come in contact with. Practice these dialogues so that you feel confident using these words and phrases in your interactions.

Giving recommendations

Phrases

- For (authentic cuisine, family activities, etc.), I recommend...
- My favorite place is...
- Personally, I suggest...

Dialogue

Tourist: Excuse me, do you know a good place for ice cream?

Guide: Oh, yes. For really good ice cream, I recommend "Maria's". It's located about six blocks from here, and it's my favorite place. Personally, I suggest the chocolate cherry flavor, but they're famous for their award-winning lemon flavor. I think your family will like it.

Tourist: Great, thanks!

Providing directions and describing places

Phrases

- Turn left
- Turn right
- Go straight
- Stop at the...
- Continue until...
- Take the (subway, bus, etc.)
- Follow the signs for...

Points of reference

- At the traffic light
- At the next (street, light, block, etc.)
- In (five) blocks
- Near the (hotel, beach, station, etc.)
- On the main plaza

Dialogue

Tourist: Can you tell me how to get to the theater?

Guide: Sure! The theater is near the train station. You need to go straight down this street for one block. At the next street, turn left. Continue until you see a sign for the theater, in about five blocks. If you're lost, you can follow the signs for the train station. Does that make sense?

Tourist: Yes, thank you!

Using simple “ice breakers” to make friendly small talk

Here are some phrases that you can use when you want to get to know the tourists a little bit better.

- So, are you enjoying your time in (Lviv) so far?
- Tell me, what is your favorite part of the city so far?
- I'm curious, do you think this city seems friendly?
- Tell me, what do/did you think of the (architecture, food, beach, festival, etc.)?

The words below are the most important words used when talking about travel when taking vacations or on holiday. Words are categorized into different sections depending on the type of travel. We give example sentences for each word to help provide context for learning, as well as short quizzes for each section.

By Air

Airport: I went to the airport to catch a flight to San Francisco.

Check-in: Make sure to get to the airport two hours early to check-in.

Fly: I like to fly on the same airlines to get mileage points.

Land: The airplane will land in two hours.

Landing: The landing took place during a storm. It was very scary!

Plane: The plane is packed with 300 passengers.

Take off: The airplane is scheduled to take off at 3:30.

Check your vocabulary by using a word to fill in the gaps:

1. My plane _____ in three hours! I have to catch a taxi to the _____.
2. Can you pick me up at tomorrow? My flight _____ at 7:30.
3. The _____ was very bumpy. I was afraid.
4. Be sure to _____ at least two hours before your flight.
5. The _____ is a 747 by Boeing.

Words for Vacations

Camp: Do you like to camp in the woods?

Destination: What is your final destination?

Excursion: I'd like to take an excursion to the wine country while we're in Tuscany.

Go camping: Let's go to the beach and go camping next weekend.

Go sightseeing: Did you go sightseeing while you were in France?

Hostel: Staying in a youth hostel is a great way to save money on vacation.

Hotel: I'll book a hotel for two nights.

Journey: The journey will take four weeks and we'll visit four countries.

Luggage: Can you carry the luggage upstairs?

Motel: We stayed in a convenient motel on our way to Chicago.

Package holiday: I prefer to buy package holidays, so I don't have to worry about anything.

Passenger: The passenger felt ill during the voyage.

Route: Our route will take us through Germany and on to Poland.

Sightseeing: The sightseeing in this town is rather boring. Let's go shopping.

Suitcase: Let me unpack my suitcase and then we can go swimming.

Tour: Peter went on a tour of vineyard.

Tourism: Tourism is becoming an important industry in almost every country.

Tourist: Every May many tourists from around the world come to see the flower festival.

Travel: Travel is one of his favorite free time activities.

Travel agent: The travel agent found us a great deal.

Trip: The trip to New York was lovely and interesting.

Vacation: I'd love to take a nice long vacation on the beach.

Use a word from the list to fill in the gaps:

1. Could I ask what your final _____ is?
2. The _____ to Chicago was very interesting.
3. I enjoy going _____ whenever I visit a new city that I don't know.
4. It's best not to take too much _____ with you on your trip. The airline might lose it!
5. There were many _____ who missed the flight to New York.
6. Let's just stay at a cheap _____ along the highway.
7. If you want to save money, take a hike and _____ in the mountains.
8. Our _____ will take us past some of the most beautiful homes in Hollywood.
9. I think _____ is one of the great ways to expand your imagination.
10. I hope your _____ was pleasant.

Travel by Land

Bicycle: One of the best ways to see the countryside is to ride a bicycle.

Bike: We rode a bike from shop to shop.

Bus: You can catch a bus for Seattle at the bus station.

Bus station: The bus station is three blocks from here.

Car: You might want to rent a car when you go on vacation.

Lane: Make sure to get into the left lane when you want to pass.

Motorcycle: Riding a motorcycle can be fun and exciting, but it's also dangerous.

Freeway: We'll have to take the freeway to Los Angeles.

Highway: The highway between the two cities is quite lovely.

Rail: Have you ever traveled by rail?

Go by rail: Going by rail offers the opportunity to get up and walk around as you travel.

Railway: The railway station is down this street.

Road: There are three roads to Denver.

Main road: Take the main road into town and turn left at 5th street.

Taxi: I got in a taxi and went to the train station.

Traffic: There's a lot of traffic today on the road!

Train: I like riding on trains. It's a very relaxing way to travel.

Tube: You can take the tube in London.

Underground: You can take the underground in many cities throughout Europe.

Subway: You can take the subway in New York.

Fill in the gaps with a target word:

1. You should change the _____ to pass this car.
2. Let's take a _____ to get to the airport.
3. I think the _____ is a great way to get around a big city.
4. Have you ever ridden a _____? It must be fun.
5. I think traveling by _____ is the best way to see the countryside. You can walk around, have dinner and just watch the world go by.
6. If you take the _____ road you will get back to town.
7. There's nothing like a _____ ride on a spring's day to get you in shape.

8. How many _____ have you owned in your life?

Sea / Ocean

Boat: Have you ever piloted a boat?

Cruise: We will stop at three destinations during our cruise through the Mediterranean.

Cruise-ship: It's the most elegant cruise-ship in the world

Ferry: Ferries allow passengers to take their cars with them to the destination.

Ocean: The Atlantic Ocean takes four days to cross.

Port: There are all kinds of commercial ships in the port.

Sailboat: The sailboat requires nothing but the wind.

Sea: The sea is very calm today.

Set sail: We set sail for the exotic island.

Ship: Have you ever been a passenger on a ship?

Voyage: The voyage to the Bahamas took three days.

Find the right word to fill in the gaps:

1. I'd love to take a fancy _____ and travel through the Bahamas.
2. It's hard to imagine that Japan is on the other side of this _____.
3. You can catch a _____ and take your car to the island.
4. We _____ next June for the cruise of a lifetime!
5. A _____ is the most environmentally friendly way to travel.
6. Let's rent a _____ for the day and row around the lake.

Conclusions Foreign languages play an important role in global hospitality management. International research has indicated their participation in the raising of customer lifetime value for the hospitality industry as well as of successful careers for future management personnel. The need to develop a competitive advantage in tourism and hospitality is even more important in Ukraine that suffers under severe economic depression. The three axes for future action - as perceived through the current study – are for the Ukrainian state to invest in foreign languages for tourism awareness and training, for educators and information technology specialists to collaborate on the development of up to date educational material making use of new technologies and the latest trends in education and for the hospitality industry to manage human capital so as to correct staffing and proficiency shortfalls in regard to foreign languages. Many young people turn to hospitality industry to combat unemployment. Fluency in more than one foreign languages is a competitive advantage in the global hospitality market taken for granted the undermining of other tourism occupational skills by fluency in foreign languages and intercultural competence as proved in the international literature. Young people have grown up surrounded by the modern technology of digital media and have developed adequate technology skills. Nurturing a tertiary level of hospitality management studies that includes a well planned foreign languages methodology could be the key to efficient language learning. Similar methodology and tools could be used by the organization of in service training seminars shifting the barriers of time and money costs and maximum performance. As eloquently illustrated in the literature review language barriers do block the way of a hospitality industry's long term success and as the global market of tourists and tourism employees increase, so does the demand for high quality foreign language for tourism specialized skills. An ongoing cooperation between hospitality industry and hospitality management education could facilitate the planning and evaluation of foreign languages for tourism courses that

depict the concrete needs students are most likely to face in their career. Lectures of human resources managers and possibility to longer apprentices to hotels abroad could empower the young students with valuable expertise and experience on the working environment conditions and demands. The field of foreign languages in hospitality management has yet to be investigated in Ukraine and it is the authors' firm belief that more studies should be carried out to evaluate and propose content and methodology.

References:

1. Blue, G. M. & Harun, M. (2003). Hospitality language as a professional skill. *English for specific purposes*, 22(1), 73-91.
2. Dudley-Evans, T., St. John, M.J.: *Developments in English for Specific Purposes: A multidisciplinary approach*. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press, 1998.
3. Frendo, E.: *How to Teach Business English*. Pearson Education, 2005.
4. Holmqvist, J., Van Vaerenbergh, Y. & Grönroos, C. (2014). Consumer willingness to communicate in a second language: Communication in service settings. *Management Decision*, 52(5), 950-966.
5. Poon, W. C., & Low, K. L. T. (2005). Are travelers satisfied with Malaysian Hotels? *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 17(3), 217-227.
6. Rwanda skills report 2012 Tourism and Hospitality Sector report, 60-70.
7. Vizental, A.: *Strategies of Teaching and Testing English as a Foreign Language*. Iasi. Editura Polirom, 2008.
8. Walter de Gruyter. Leslie, D. & Russell, H. (2006). The importance of foreign language skills in the tourism sector: A comparative study of student perceptions in the UK and continental Europe. *Tourism Management*, 27(6), 1397-1407.
9. Zorina, N. M., Maslennikova, E. G. & Gazilov, M. G. (2014). The Formation of Intercultural Competence as an Integral Part of Professional Training in the Field of Tourism. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 30(MCTT), 41-42.